

Experimental

Preparation of 1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S-p-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets (II): 1-Substituted thiocarbamides were alkylated with *p*-Cl-benzyl chloride. Benzene solution of the 1-substituted-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzylisothiocarbamide free bases were condensed with the appropriate aryl or alkylisothiocyanates resulting in the formation of the corresponding 1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

The details of a representative experiment are as follows: 1-Phenylthiocarbamide (5g) was alkylated with *p*-Cl-benzylchloride following Werner's procedure⁴. 1-Phenyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzylisothiocarbamide hydrochloride thus obtained was cooled and basified with ammonium hydroxide solution when the free base separated as a solid compound. The product was filtered and dried (yield 9g, 76.5%). Benzene solution of 1-phenyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzylisothiocarbamide was mixed with *p*-tolylisothiocyanate (4.7g) in 1:1 mole and refluxed for 1 hr on a water-bath. The semisolid mass so obtained on evaporation of the solvent, was washed with petroleum ether and on addition of a little ethanol, afforded a crystalline mass (yield 8.2g, 63%). It was recrystallised

from ethanol m.p. 95°. These compounds are listed in Table-1.

3,5-Diaryl/arylalkyl-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines(IV) Oxidative de-*p*-chlorobenzoylation of 1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets with bromine in chloroform: molecular bromine readily effected de-*p*-chlorobenzoylation of 1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso 4-thiobiurets in a little chloroform solution followed by ring closure to the related 3,5-diaryl/arylalkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrobromides. For example: 1-phenyl-5-*m*-tolyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (3g) was moistened with chloroform (1 ml) and was treated with bromine (1.5g) until colour of bromine persisted. The reaction mixture warmed up considerably evolving fumes of *p*-chlorobenzylbromide. After standing the mixture for 30 minutes, the semi solid product was washed first with ether, then with ether containing a little ethanol, when the hydrobromide of the oxidation product separated as a crystalline mass. On treatment with ammonia, the free base was obtained, which was filtered, dried and thoroughly washed with ether (yield 2.3g, 75%). It was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 185°. The melting point, yield and elemental analysis of these compounds are given in Table-2.

 TABLE 1—PREPARATION OF 1,5-DIARYL/ARYLALKYL-2-S-*p*-CL-BENZYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS (II)

1-Substituted-2-S- <i>p</i> -Cl-benzylisothiocarbamide	Isothiocyanate	1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S- <i>p</i> -Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret formed	M. P.	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1-phenyl-2-S-T	<i>p</i> -tolylisothiocyanate	1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-B	95	63	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	C : 61.91 H : 4.74 N : 9.71	62.04 4.70 9.87
1-phenyl-2-S-T	<i>m</i> -tolylisothiocyanate	1-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-B	116	61	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	C : 62.36 H : 4.42 N : 9.65	62.04 4.70 9.87
1-phenyl-2-S-T	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenylisothiocyanate	1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl-B	103	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	N : 8.74 S : 13.39	8.90 13.57
1-phenyl-2-S-T	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenylisothiocyanate	1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-B	120	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂	N : 9.27 S : 14.03	9.41 14.35
1-phenyl-2-S-T	Ethylisothiocyanate	1-phenyl-5-ethyl-B	—	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	—	—

Where T—represents—*p*-Cl-benzylisothiocarbamides and B—represents—2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

Typical ir frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 1-phenyl-5-*m*-tolyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret :

3166 m, NH stretching (Lit.⁶ 3400-3100), 1105 m, 1175 w, N-C(=S)-N grouping (Lit.^{5a} 1200-1100); 1595 m, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{5b} 1685-1582); 1375 vs, C=S grouping (Lit.⁶ 1400-1100); 700s shows "iso" form in isodithiobiuret chain, 1425 w, CH₂-S deformation (Lit., 1435-1410)^{5a, 7}.

TABLE 2—3,5-DIARYL/ARYLALKYLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES (IV) : OXIDATION OF 1,5-DIARYL/ARYLALKYL-2-S-*p*-CL-BENZYL-ISO-4-THIOBIURETS WITH BROMINE IN CHLOROFORM.

1,5-diaryl/aryl-alkyl-2-S- <i>p</i> -Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets	5-Arylimino-3-aryl/alkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines formed	M. P.	Yield %	Molecular formulae	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-B	5-phenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-D	175	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	N : 14.31	14.05
1-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-B	5-phenylimino-3- <i>m</i> -tolylimino-D	185	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂	N : 14.21 S : 21.05	14.05 21.40
1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl-B	5-phenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenylimino-D	161	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂ O	C : 59.63 H : 4.68 N : 12.53	59.71 4.55 12.76
1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-B	5-phenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-D	184-85*	78	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	C : 52.71 H : 3.21 N : 13.01	52.58 3.13 13.14
1-phenyl-5-ethyl-B	5-phenylimino-3-ethylimino-D	141	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂	N : 17.51 S : 26.84	17.72 27.01

Where B=2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets and
D=1,2,4-dithiazolidine.

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Typical ir frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 5-phenylimino-3-*m*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine :

Ring-C-S (700 m)⁸, C=N (1588 s)⁶, ring-S-S-linkage (500 m)⁷.

Reduction of 3,5-diaryl/arylalkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines by ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide : The dithiazolidines were dissolved in ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 20-30 mins. The clear solution on dilution with water or acidification afforded the corresponding dithiobiuret. These were recrystallised from ethanol. The identity of each product was established by observing undepressed mixed melting points with the authentic sample obtained by the reductive de-*p*-Cl-benylation of the isodithiobiurets (II) with hydrogen sulphide in ethanolic-ammoniacal solution. These were further characterised by superimposable I. R. spectra.

*Reductive de-*p*-Cl-benylation of 1, 5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2-S-*p*-Cl-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets by alkaline hydrogen sulphide to the corresponding 2,4-dithiobiurets :* The isodithiobiurets (II) were dissolved

in ethanolic solution of sodium sulphide (10 per cent) and a stream of hydrogen sulphide was passed for 3 hrs. The resulting solution on filtration and neutralization with acetic acid yielded the dithiobiurets (III). These were recrystallised from ethanol.

Oxidation of 1,5-diaryl/arylalkyl-2,4-dithiobiurets to the corresponding 3,5-diaryl/arylalkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines : The dithiobiurets (III) were oxidised with bromine in ethanolic solution and on addition of ether the hydrobromides of the respective dithiazolidines precipitated. Free bases were obtained by treating these with ammonia and were recrystallised from ethanol and chlorobenzene. These were found to be identical with the respective 3,5-diaryl/arylalkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (IV). The identity was further confirmed by ir spectra and mixture melting point technique.

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